

CHICKENPOX: AMONG YOUNG CHILDREN IN KHOREZM REGION

OTAJANOV SH.Z., ARTIQOV I.A., ABDULLAYEVA D.K.

Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy

✓ **Resume**

Varicella is not a harmless disease; a certain percentage of various complications are recorded, including those requiring subsequent hospitalization. Moreover, this is observed in children under the age of 15 years with normal immunity. With age, the risk of complications and mortality can increase up to 50%, provided that the sick adult has not had varicella before or has not been vaccinated. Often, secondary skin infections, pneumonia, varicella encephalitis, cerebellar ataxia, lesion of the facial nerve, and eye damage are recorded as complications.

Keywords: vaccine, herpes, varicella, rash, immunity, temperature, skin, infection.

Introduction

Chickenpox is an extremely contagious acute infectious disease. The causative agent of chickenpox, a DNA-containing virus, causes the development of two diseases: chickenpox upon first contact with the virus and shingles upon reactivation of the virus in the body of a previously ill person [4]. The causative agent of chickenpox is the Varicella zoster virus, which belongs to the family of herpes viruses. In the external environment, the virus is unstable and quickly dies [1]. The only source of infection is humans.

The susceptibility to chickenpox is very high. The entrance gate of infection is the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract. Viruses are released in large numbers when sneezing, coughing, or talking. Transmission of the virus from mother to fetus during pregnancy is also possible [5].

Despite the fact that children of mostly preschool age remain the most vulnerable category in terms of chickenpox incidence, adults can also get sick [2]. At the same time, do not forget that the disease in adults is fraught with the development of severe complications, the most common of which is pneumonia. The urgency of the problem of chickenpox is determined by the high contagiousness, widespread occurrence of this disease, and the risk of complications, especially in adults [3].

Purpose of the study

To analyze the epidemiological features of chickenpox among children in the Khorezm region.

Research materials and methods

In order to study the symptoms of the clinical manifestation of chickenpox in modern conditions, we have analyzed the archival medical records of 46 children with chickenpox under 1 year old who were hospitalized at the regional clinical Infectious Diseases hospital in Urgench in the period from 2018 to 2022.

Chickenpox is an acute, highly contagious infectious disease accompanied by an increase in body temperature and the appearance of a characteristic blotchy rash on the surface of the skin and mucous membranes. The susceptibility to chickenpox is exceptionally high — almost 100%. Children

under 7 years of age and primary school age are more susceptible to the disease. Children of the first 2-3 months of life and older than 10 years, as well as adults, rarely suffer from chickenpox, since specific antibodies are present in their bodies. Chickenpox in children can also occur in newborns due to the lack of immunity in the mother.

A high number of cases of chickenpox occur in the cold season — in autumn and winter. In summer, the incidence is significantly reduced. A characteristic feature of chickenpox is the occurrence of epidemic outbreaks, most often in children's organized groups (in preschool organizations). After the child suffers from this disease, he develops a stable immune system. Recurrent diseases occur very rarely (about 3% of cases).

In 10-20% of patients, the varicella zoster virus remains in the nerve ganglia for life and subsequently causes another disease that can manifest itself at an older age - shingles or Herpes zoster. Herpes zoster is characterized by prolonged and excruciating neuralgic pain, and also has a number of complications in the form of lesions of the nervous system and internal organs – paralysis, visual impairment.

People with herpes zoster can be a source of chickenpox infection.

Chickenpox can also cause damage to the fetus or newborn when a woman gets chickenpox in the first 20 weeks of pregnancy or in the last days before giving birth.

Vaccination against chickenpox in children and adults provides an opportunity to prevent these consequences. There is a low risk of post-vaccination infection in people with severe immunodeficiency (oncohematology, etc.), but in any case, vaccination of these people against chickenpox in developed countries is carried out as a standard procedure for the prevention of severe chickenpox.

Results of the study

The main group of children with chickenpox was 35 (76.0%) children over 3 months of age. The proportion of chickenpox in the group of children under 3 months was 11 patients (24%), from 3 to 6 months – 12 patients (26%). In the group of children aged 6 to 9 months, there were 10 patients (21.7%) and 13 patients (28.3%) aged 9 months to 1 year.

The frequency of chickenpox did not depend on the gender of the affected children: There were 25 girls (54%) and 21 boys (46%). Of the 46 children who contracted chickenpox, only 35 (76.0%) had contact with chickenpox patients. On the first day of the disease, 20 (43.5%) children were admitted, on day 2 – 12 (26.0%), on day 3 – 8 (17.4%) children. After 3 days of the onset of the disease, only 6 children were admitted, which accounted for 13.0% of the number of cases.

In 30 (65.2%) patients, body temperature rose to 38° C, in 11 (23.9%) – to 39° C, and in 5 (10.9%), body temperature was above 39°C. The mild form of the disease was registered in 78% of cases, the moderate form in 18% and the severe form in 4%. Polymorphic vesicular rash was observed in all patients. The course of the disease was undulating and it was for this reason that the rashes appeared with a frequency of up to several times.

Discussion

The study confirms the high susceptibility of children to chickenpox, especially in the first year of life. The data obtained correlate with previous studies showing an increase in incidence in organized children's groups. The predominance of mild cases suggests that, despite the high infectivity of the disease, most young children develop a relatively benign course of infection. However, the presence of moderate and severe cases underlines the need for preventive measures, including vaccination, to reduce the burden of the disease. The seasonal peak in the cold months also emphasizes the importance of heightened surveillance during autumn and winter.

Conclusions

Thus, it should be noted that in recent years, there has been an increase in the incidence of chickenpox in children under 1 year of age. The clinical picture of chickenpox retains its typical features. In infants and young children, a mild form of the disease prevails.

List of literature.

1. Masharipov, S., Sadullaev, S. E., & Sh, M. D. (2023). THE COURSE OF CORONAVIRUS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS. Scientific Impulse, 2(15), 65-70.
2. Masharipova Sh.S, Masharipov S, Sadullaev S.E, & Matyakubova D.Sh. (2023). THE COURSE OF CORONAVIRUS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS. Scientific Impulse, 2(15), 65–70. Retrieved from
3. Sadullayev S. E. et al. THE COURSE OF NOSOCOMIAL PNEUMONIA IN PATIENTS ON LONG-TERM ARTIFICIAL LUNG VENTILATION //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 26. – С. 80-84.
4. Машарипова Шохиста Сабириевна, Артиков Икром Ахмеджанович, Матякубова Ойша Уриновна РАСТРОЙСТВА ПСИХИКИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ДЕСТРУКТИВНЫМИ ФОРМАМИ ТУБЕРКУЛЕЗА В УСЛОВИЯХ ПАНДЕМИИ COVID-19 // JCRR. 2021. №3.
URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rastroystva-psihihi-u-bolnyh-destruktivnymi-formami-tuberkuleza-v-usloviyah-pandemii-covid-19>
5. Машарипова Шохиста Сабириевна МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ ЛЕГОЧНЫХ АРТЕРИЙ ПОД ВЛИЯНИЕМ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА // JCRR. 2022. №1.
URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/morfologicheskoe-stroenie-legochnyh-arteriy-pod-vliyanem-saharnogo-diabeta>
6. Туйчиев Л. Н. и др. A study of the factors affecting the effectiveness of COVID-19 rehabilitation. – 2023.
7. Машарипова Ш. С. О ‘РКА АРТЕРИЯЛАРИНИНГ QANDLI ДИАБЕТ ТА’СИРИДА МОРФОЛОГИК ТУЗИЛИШИ //Журнал кардиореспираторных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1.
8. Yusupov Sh.Sh, Ibrakhimova H.R, & Masharipova Sh.S. (2023). IMMUNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WHOSE BODY IS INFECTED WITH CATTLE

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

SOLITAIRE. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(15), 120–124. извлечено от <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/12430>

9. Ibrakhimova H.R, Masharipova Sh.S, & Artikov I.A. (2023). CHANGES IN THE IMMUNE STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH PARASITIC DISEASE. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(15), 103–108. извлечено от <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/12427>

10. Masharipova Sh.S, Masharipov S, & Matyakubova D.Sh. (2023). UDC:616.36-005:75-642 TUBERCULOSIS AND ITS COURSE IN PATIENTS WITH HEPATITIS B. Scientific Impulse, 2(14), 95–99. Retrieved from <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/12215>

11. Masharipova Sh.S, Ibrakhimova H.R, & Nurlayev R.R. (2023). A METHOD FOR OBTAINING PRECIPITATING SERUMS FOR THE DETECTION OF HUMAN SEMINAL FLUID USED IN THE STUDY OF PHYSICAL EVIDENCE IN FORENSIC BIOLOGICAL LABORATORIES. World Bulletin of Management and Law, 19, 42–44. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/2119>

12. IMMUNE STATUS IN PATIENTS WITH PARASITIC DISEASES IN KHOREZM REGION. (2025). Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 5(1), 514–517. <http://www.mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/2518>

13. Машарипов С.М., Юсупов Ш.Р., Машарипова Ш.С., Матякубова О.У. КЛИНИЧЕСКОЕ ТЕЧЕНИЕ ТУБЕРКУЛЕЗА У БОЛЬНЫХ ГЕПАТИТОМ В / Вестник ТМА.uz. 2023 г. № 3 (2) – стр. 155-157.

14. Аскарлова Р.И., Юсупов Ш.Р., Машарипова Ш.С., Машарипова Х.К. Эпидемиология легочного туберкулеза/EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY LVII International correspondence scientific and practical conference. 2019/Издательство: PROBLEMS OF SCIENCE / United Kingdom, 06–07 ноября 2019 год, стр. 96-100

15. S., M. S., E., S. S. ., J., I. S. ., I., Q. N. ., & B., B. Y. . (2024). THE SPREAD OF CHICKENPOX AMONG THE POPULATION. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 3(3), 48–54. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/2302>

16. Masharipova Sh.S, Ibadullayeva S.S, Yakubov K.Y, & Artikov I.A. (2024). FEATURES OF INFECTIOUS MONONUCLEOSIS IN CHILDREN. Scientific Impulse, 2(16), 1165–1171. Retrieved from <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/14208>

17. Masharipova Sh.S, Ibadullayeva S.S, Yakubov K.Y and Artikov I.A 2024. FEATURES OF INFECTIOUS MONONUCLEOSIS IN CHILDREN. Scientific Impulse. 2, 16 (Jan. 2024), 1165–1171.

18. Садуллаев, С. Е., Машарипова, Ш. С., & Машарипов, С. (2023). КЛИНИКО-ЛАБОРАТОРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕЧЕНИЯ ПНЕВМОНИИ, АССОЦИИРОВАННОЙ С COVID-19, У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА. Международный журнал образования,

социальных и гуманитарных наук. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(9), 851-856.

19. Сабировна, Ш., & Машарипова, А. И. А. Садуллаев Сирож Эрназарович, и Абдуллаева Дилфуза Кадамовна. 2022.«ТЕЧЕНИЕ КОРОНАВИРУСНОЙ ИНФЕКЦИИ НА ФОНЕ ГЕПАТИТОВ». Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке 1 (5): 573-77. ТЕЧЕНИЕ КОРОНАВИРУСНОЙ ИНФЕКЦИИ НА ФОНЕ ГЕПАТИТОВ». Новости образования.

20. Masharipova Sh.S, Masharipov S, & Matyakubova D.Sh. (2023). UDC:616.36-005:75-642 TUBERCULOSIS AND ITS COURSE IN PATIENTS WITH HEPATITIS B. Scientific Impulse, 2(14), 95–99. Retrieved from <https://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/12215>

21. Masharipova Sh.S, Masharipov S, & Matyakubova D.Sh. (2023). UDC:616.36-005:75-642 TUBERCULOSIS AND ITS COURSE IN PATIENTS WITH HEPATITIS B. Scientific Impulse, 2(14), 95–99. Retrieved from <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/12215>

22. Masharipova Shokhista Sabirovna, & Masharipov Sobir. (2023). UDC: 619:616.995.132.6 IMMUNE STATUS OF ADULTS AND CHILDREN WITH AN ALLERGIC BACKGROUND DIAGNOSED WITH ENTEROBIOSIS. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(14), 24–28. извлечено от <https://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/noiv/article/view/11911>

23. CHARACTERISTICS OF PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN LYMPHOCYTIC LEUKOSIS IN CHILDREN. (2023). Western European Journal of Medicine and Medical Science, 1(4), 21-26. <https://westerneuropeanstudies.com/index.php/3/article/view/122>

24. RESULTS OF STUDIES ON THE LEVEL OF POPULATION KNOWLEDGE ABOUT PARASITIC DISEASES AND ITS PREVENTION. (2023). Western European Journal of Medicine and Medical Science, 1(4), 15-20. <https://westerneuropeanstudies.com/index.php/3/article/view/121>

25. THE STRUCTURE OF COMORBID PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN WITH COVID-19. (2024). CONFERENCE ON THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF SCIENCE IN THE MODERN WORLD, 1(2), 27-28.

26. Sadullaev S. E., Sh M. D. THE COURSE OF CORONAVIRUS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS Masharipova Sh. S Masharipov S //Научный импульс. – 2023. – С. 78.

27. Ibrakhimova, H. R., Sadullaev, S. E., & Nurllayev, R. R. (2023). SPREAD OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AMONG THE POPULATION OF THE KHOREZM REGION. IMRAS, 6(7), 328-332.

28. Ibraximova H. R., Sadullayev S. E. AHOLI ORASIDA O ‘TKIR ICHAK KASALLIKLARINING TARQALISHI //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 15. – С. 115-119.

29. Ибрахимова ХР, Матьякубова ОУ, Садуллаев СЭ и Абдуллаева ДК (2023). ГЕЛЬМИНТЫ У ДЕТЕЙ СРЕДИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА. IMRAS, 6(7), 323–327. Получено с <https://journal.imras.org/index.php/sps/article/view/521>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

30. Artikov, I. A., Sadullaev, S. E., Ibrakhimova, H. R., & Abdullayeva, D. K. (2023). *RELEVANCE OF VIRAL HEPATITIS EPIDEMIOLOGY. IMRAS*, 6 (7), 316–322.
31. Tuychiev, L. N., Khudaykulova, G. K., Eraliev, U. E., Djuraeva, N. K., & Sadullaev, S. E. (2023). A STUDY OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COVID-19 REHABILITATION.
32. Sadullaev S. E., Sh M. D. THE COURSE OF CORONAVIRUS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS Masharipova Sh. S Masharipov S //Научный импульс. – 2023. – С. 78.
33. Туйчиев, Л. Н., Худайкулова, Г. К., Джураева, Н., & Эралиев, У. Э. (2023). A study of the factors affecting the effectiveness of COVID-19 rehabilitation.
34. Sadullaev M., Sh S. M. D. THE COURSE OF CORONAVIRUS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS. – 2023.
35. Nurullayev R. R., Sadullayev S. E. DIAREYALI KASALLIKLARNING EPIDYEMIOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI //World of Science. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 9. – С. 64-67.
36. Эралиев, У. Э., & Садуллаев, С. Э. (2020). Molecular genetic characteristics of rotavirus infection in children. Молодой ученый, (38), 46-48.
37. ANALYSIS OF THE EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF DIARRHEAL DISEASES IN CHILDREN IN THE SOUTHERN ARAL REGION. (2024). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 345-351. <http://www.mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/870>
38. Рахматуллаева, Ш.Б. Особенности течения COVID-19 у детей с коморбидной патологией // Ш.Б. Рахматуллаева, М.Т. Муминова, А.Х. Нурматов и др. // Педиатрия. Восточная Европа. - 2023. № 3 12. - 436-442. - https://recipe.by/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/436-442_ped_3-2024-v12.pdf (дата обращения: 26.03.2025). doi: 10.34883/PI.2024.12.3.006
39. INTESTINAL IMMUNITY. (2025). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(2), 485-488. <https://mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/2691>
40. PSYCHOLOGICAL REHABILITATION DURING THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC. (2025). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(2), 429-433. <http://www.mjstjournal.com/index.php/mjst/article/view/2678>
41. THE STRUCTURE OF COMORBID PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN WITH COVID-19. (2024). *CONFERENCE ON THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF SCIENCE IN THE MODERN WORLD*, 1(2), 27-28. <https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/crismw/article/view/641>